

Report of the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 22 April 2002

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**REPORT OF THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
8 April 2002**

To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. We wish to inform you that we have witnessed an event in which the IRA leadership has put a varied and substantial quantity of ammunition, arms and explosive material beyond use. In accordance with the Governments' Scheme and Regulations, we have made an inventory of the arms concerned, which we will provide to the two governments when our task is completed.
2. As before, we have agreed to the IRA's condition of confidentiality regarding details of this event, as provided for in the same Scheme and Regulations.
3. We will continue our discussions with the IRA representative in the pursuit of our remit. We will also continue our discussions with the loyalist paramilitary groups.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 8 April 2002

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